

Solid-Liquid Separation (SLS) of Animal Manure and Climate Outcomes: Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart
Agricultural Practices

June 30, 2025

ABOUT THE TECHNICAL ADVISORY NETWORK FOR CLIMATE SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

WORKING GROUP	CHAIRPERSON	PRIMARY AFFILIATION	EMAIL
Agroforestry	Dr. Nate Lawrence	Savanna Institute	nate@savannainstitute.org
Enteric Methane	Dr. Ermias Kebreab	University of California, Davis	ekebreab@ucdavis.edu
Grazing Lands	Dr. Jennifer Watts	Woodwell Climate Research Center	jwatts@woodwellclimate.org
Nutrient Management	Dr. Justin Baker	North Carolina State University	jsbaker4@ncsu.edu
Manure Management	Dr. Rebecca Larson	University of Wisconsin-Madison	rebecca.larson@wisc.edu
Soil Carbon	Dr. Bruno Basso	Michigan State University	basso@msu.edu

Technical Work Group Members*Solid Liquid Separation Workstream:*

Horacio Aguirre-Villegas, Scientist III, Nelson Institute for Environmental Studies, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Deanne Meyer, Cooperative Extension Specialist and Lecturer, Animal Science, University of California-Davis

Mahmoud Sharara, Associate Professor and Extension Specialist, Biological and Agricultural Engineering, North Carolina State University

Acidification Workstream:

Rebecca Larson (Chair), Professor and Extension Specialist, Nelson Institute for Environmental Studies, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Meredith Niles, Professor, Department of Nutrition and Food Sciences, University of Vermont

Swati Hegde, Manager, Agricultural Methane, World Resources Institute

Research Assistant

Edward Boswell, Teaching Faculty, University of Wisconsin

Meridian Team

Candace Spencer, Mediator and Program Manager

Mark Jacobs, Senior Mediator and Program Director

Gabriel Lobet, Project Associate II and Ruckelshaus Fellow

Citation:

Aguirre-Villegas, Horacio, Rebecca Larson, Deanne Meyer, Mahmoud Sharara, Meredith Niles, and Swati Hegde. "Solid-Liquid Separation (SLS) of Animal Manure and Climate Outcomes: Technical Guidance." 2025. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15777985.

DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15777985

Disclaimer: The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the listed authors and do not necessarily reflect the views or positions of all participants in the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agriculture Practices.

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	4
GOAL AND SCOPE	4
BACKGROUND	4
REPORTING GHG EMISSIONS FROM MANURE MANAGEMENT	5
FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO GHG MITIGATION BEFORE, DURING, AND AFTER SLS	5
FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS BEFORE SLS - UPSTREAM	8
FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS DURING THE SLS PROCESS	9
FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS AFTER SLS - DOWNSTREAM	10
RESEARCH EVIDENCE FOR GHG EMISSION REDUCTIONS AFTER SLS	11
PRACTICE IMPLEMENTATION	13
SUMMARY	14
ADDITIONAL RESOURCES	15
APPENDIX	15
A. ESTIMATION OF SEPARATION EFFICIENCY	15
B. EQUATION TO ESTIMATE CH ₄ EMISSIONS FROM SLURRY/LIQUID MANURE STORAGE	16
C. MEASURING, MONITORING, REPORTING, AND VERIFYING (MMRV) STRATEGIES FOR GHGs AFTER SLS	16
D. NEEDS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH	16
REFERENCES	17

Introduction

GOAL AND SCOPE

This document aims to provide conservation specialists and individuals in similar roles, background on the practice of manure solid-liquid separation (SLS), its goals, and the factors that influence its effectiveness. The focus is on SLS as a greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation strategy for animal farms. The recommendations provided in this document also support the implementation of SLS for other goals, including improved nutrient management.

SLS is relevant to farms where manure is managed and stored anaerobically as liquid or slurry, which are typically dairy or swine farms. The intent is to separate larger sized solids from the liquid waste stream thereby relocating carbon and nutrients from liquid to solid form. SLS is not an applicable practice for poultry farms that employ bedding or rely on belt-systems in which manure is promptly dried; beef feedlots that manage manure in solid form; or small dairy or swine farms that rely on pens, lots, or pastures to raise animals and subsequently store manure as solids, or directly deposit manure on fields, therefore eliminating the need for SLS.

This report focuses on:

- Farm operations managing slurry or liquid manure, mostly dairy and swine farms.
- Storage of separated manure, as well as use of separated solids and liquids.
- Methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions.
- Ammonia (NH₃), since it can be a precursor to N₂O emissions.

BACKGROUND

SLS is a common wastewater treatment practice. Historically, it was developed to separate suspended and dissolved solids from wastewater to allow further water treatment and discharge. The practice was adapted to animal farms to improve manure management on larger farms. This practice involves splitting a liquid manure volume into two parts: solid fraction and liquid fraction, each with different physical and chemical (nutrient) properties. Adding an SLS system involves additional capital and operational costs to the farm.

SLS systems are often adopted to:

- Reduce treatment volume required in aerobic or anaerobic lagoons, since the treatment volume is dependent on organic solids loading in the liquid entering the lagoon.
- Reduce sludge accumulation in lagoons or tanks, therefore reduce annual cost associated with storage cleanout.
- Create a drier, nutrient-dense material (solid fraction) conducive to export.

- Facilitate application of custom manure nutrient ratios (nitrogen-phosphorus-potassium) by adjusting the ratio of solid and liquid fractions used and thereby reducing commercial fertilizer purchases.

In addition to these benefits, SLS can also help reduce GHG emissions associated with manure management.

WHAT DRIVES GHG EMISSIONS FROM MANURE?

When manure is stored as a liquid or slurry, anaerobic (without oxygen) conditions prevail. These conditions promote growth of methane-forming bacteria (methanogens), which feed on organic solids and produce CH₄. The activity of methanogenic bacteria, and production of CH₄, depends on environmental factors, such as temperature, pH, and organic solids quantity. Anaerobic conditions also promote the decomposition of manure crude protein into amino acids and ultimately soluble ammonium (NH₄⁺). NH₄⁺ is the direct source of ammonia (NH₃) in manure systems, with the emission rate of NH₃ driven by temperature, wind speed, and the concentration of NH₄⁺ in the storage. Conversely, solid manure stored and managed in aerobic (with oxygen) conditions favor aerobic bacteria that convert organic solids to carbon dioxide (CO₂), a much lower GHG potency gas than CH₄. Rapid drying of solid manure can interrupt aerobic bacteria, thereby reducing CO₂ emissions and conserving the carbon in organic solids. In situations where manure conditions allow alternating aerobic and anaerobic conditions, N₂O emissions are increased.

Reporting GHG Emissions from Manure Management

GHG emissions from manure management are typically reported in mass of carbon dioxide equivalents (kg CO₂-eq). This unit standardizes the warming strengths of CH₄ and N₂O to that of CO₂, allowing for consistent comparisons (one molecule of CH₄ has the same GHG effect as 26 to 28 molecules of CO₂; while one molecule of N₂O has the same GHG effect as 298 molecules of CO₂ over a 100-year period (Forster et al., 2021)).

Total emissions are generally reported over a specific period (e.g., kg CO₂-eq per year or day), but most studies report GHG emissions as an intensity, often referred to as carbon intensity (CI). Carbon intensity is calculated by dividing total GHG emissions by the unit of product or activity provided by the farm (e.g., kilograms of milk, meat, or manure). GHGs can also be reported at various levels: for the entire farm, for all manure handling operations, or for individual operations (e.g., storage). It is essential to clearly specify the scope when reporting emissions.

Factors that Contribute to GHG mitigation before, during, and after SLS

GHG and NH₃ emissions are influenced both directly and indirectly when an SLS system is installed at a farm. These factors come into play before (upstream), during, and after (downstream) the separation

process and can be categorized into three main groups: management-related, technical, and environmental (**Table 1**). The overall net effect of the SLS process on GHGs depends on the interaction between these factors.

Table 1. Individual drivers of methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and ammonia (NH₃) emissions before (upstream), during, and after (downstream) the SLS processing of animal manure. Upward arrows indicate increased gas emissions from the driving factor, downward arrows a decrease, and hyphens a neutral effect, increase or decrease gas emissions, or no information on the effect.

Stage	Aspect	Driving factor	Gas	Explanation	
Upstream from the SLS process	Management	Animal characteristics	CH ₄ - N ₂ O - NH ₃ -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composition of feed and quantity of feed intake varies by production level within species. Smaller animals eat less and excrete less than their mature counterparts. For dairy, replacement animals can be fed high fiber diets from 6 to 22 months of age. 	
		Herd diet	CH ₄ - N ₂ O - NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher fiber concentration decreases digestibility and NH₃ emissions, increases VS excretion and CH₄ potential to be emitted Higher lignin in the diet (dairy) reduces CH₄ potential. Higher crude protein (nitrogen) yields higher nitrogen excreted in manure (typically as increased urea) increases emissions. Higher by-product inclusion decreases particle size in excreted manure (dairy). Supplementation with enteric CH₄ inhibitors may have carryover effects in manure. 	
		Manure management before SLS	CH ₄ - N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher N content in manure yields higher NH₃ and N₂O potential. 	
		Additions to manure (e.g., bedding, wastewater and feed)	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bedding physical and chemical composition and quantity adds to waste stream and influences effectiveness of SLS system. 	
		Retention time before separation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> See (Holding Tank). 	
		Housing cleaning	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delaying the collection of manure from barns can increase the likelihood of gas emissions. 	
		Flush frequency		CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O - NH ₃ -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Frequent flushes reduce establishment of methanogenic bacteria in freshly excreted manure. Frequent flushes increase opportunities for NH₃ release. Frequent flushes in dairy may decrease NH₃ release by collecting urea and/or NH₄⁺ and storing in liquid system.

		Holding tank (or collection box/pit)	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O - NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extended storage period prior to separation increases CH₄ and NH₃ potential emissions. Residual material in holding tank acts as bacteria starters to promote microbial decomposition and emissions.
	Environmental	Temperature	CH ₄ ↑- N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Warmer climates increase microbial activity and emissions from housing area before SLS. However, sustained high temperatures (>50 °C) can stress methanogenic microorganisms and CH₄ production can decrease or stop.
		Wind speed	CH ₄ - N ₂ O - NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher windspeeds increase air exchange thereby increasing NH₃ emission rates from housing before SLS.
During the SLS process	Management	Calibration and maintenance	CH ₄ ↓ NH ₃ ↓ N ₂ O ↓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Routine calibration and maintenance maintain separation efficiency which reduces GHG and NH₃ emissions.
		Technical	Separation efficiency	CH ₄ ↓ NH ₃ ↓ N ₂ O ↓
		Process duration	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extended separation period, as in gravity settling basins and lanes, increase emission potential for all relevant gases.
	Environmental	Temperature	CH ₄ ↑- N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elevated temperatures promote increased emissions from hold tanks and settling basins/lanes used for separation. However, sustained high temperatures (>50 °C) can stress methanogenic microorganisms and CH₄ production can decrease or stop.
Downstream from the SLS process	Management	Storage surface area (solids and liquids)	CH ₄ - N ₂ O NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A greater manure surface area (due to more volume) increases nitrogen exposure to air and wind, which increases NH₃ losses.
		Organic crust acting as cover during storage (liquid)	CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A crust creates aerobic (with oxygen) conditions on the storage surface, limiting CH₄ emissions. Mix of aerobic and anaerobic (without oxygen) conditions promote N₂O formation and emissions. A crust acts as a barrier to wind and reduces NH₃ losses.
		Storage duration (solid and liquid)	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prolonged static manure storage increases the likelihood of CH₄, N₂O, and NH₃ formation and emissions, particularly during warmer conditions. Regular turning of solids (composting) increases the likelihood of N₂O and NH₃ emissions and formation of nitrate.
		pH (solid and liquid)	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High pH promotes growth of bacteria responsible for NH₃ and N₂O formation, while neutral pH promotes CH₄ formation and emission.
		Moisture (solid)	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased moisture levels in separated solid manure creates anaerobic conditions, promoting N₂O emissions.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extended wet periods promote mineralization of organic nitrogen which increases NH₃ release.
	Mixing or turning (solid)	CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aeration of manure promotes aerobic conditions that inhibit the activity of CH₄ producing bacteria, but it can also create a mix of aerobic and anaerobic conditions that promote the growth of N₂O producing bacteria. Aeration of manure accelerates NH₃ loss and can increase manure pH.
	Injection or rapid incorporation	CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Soil pH is typically lower than optimal range for methanogens, which reduces methane emissions. Injection can increase soil moisture and create a mix of aerobic and anaerobic conditions that favor N₂O emissions. Injection limits the access of nitrogen to the atmosphere and facilitates retention of nitrogen into the soil, reducing the potential for NH₃ loss after land application.
	Inspection and monitoring	CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O ↓ NH ₃ ↓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular inspection and monitoring of storage and land application structures and equipment enables early detection of issues (e.g., leaks) that could increase emissions.
Technical	Separated volatile solids that go along with solid fraction	CH ₄ ↓ N ₂ O - NH ₃ -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid storage: Reduced volatile solids limit CH₄ emission Solid storage: Aerobic conditions limit CH₄ emissions. Anaerobic conditions increase CH₄ and N₂O.
Environmental	Temperature	CH ₄ ↑- N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High temperatures increase the activity of bacteria responsible for producing both CH₄ and N₂O. However, sustained high temperatures (>50 °C) can stress methanogenic microorganisms and CH₄ production can decrease or stop. Nitrogen is converted to ammonia gas at higher temperatures.
	Rainfall	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ ↑	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased moisture in separated solids promotes anaerobic pockets, increasing both CH₄ and N₂O emissions. Increased surface liquid manure storage area increases NH₃
	Relative humidity	CH ₄ ↑ N ₂ O ↑ NH ₃ -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greater relative humidity reduces drying in solid stacks which increase anaerobic conditions. Alternating low and high relative humidity can create aerobic-anaerobic cycles which promote N₂O release.

FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS BEFORE SLS - UPSTREAM

Chemical and physical characteristics of manure (feces and urine) are influenced by dietary ingredients. Dairy facilities using a high proportion of byproduct feeds (waste stream from processing human food for consumption) have smaller particle sizes in manure (Meyer, personal observation) than facilities

feeding long hay and forages. In swine, by contrast, the particle size of feed rations showed no effect on manure solids particle size distribution (Jett et al., 1974). Swine diets high in fiber (cellulose) increase carbon content (Kerr et al., 2006) which increases the potential for CH₄ emissions. Additionally, manure modification occurs when animals increase nutrient use (less nutrient in manure). Current feed additives promoted to reduce enteric CH₄ emissions may or may not have a carryover effect on manure CH₄ emissions. Predictors of CH₄ emissions from dairy manure included concentration of dry matter, volatile solids (VS) and lignin (Hilgert et al., 2023).

Animal housing and management define the quantity of recoverable manure in liquid or slurry form. Time on concrete (TOC) is used as a surrogate to estimate the percentage of excreted manure collected in liquid or slurry form (Cohen-Davidyan et al., 2020). Values range from less than 8% TOC in pasture systems (manure collected two hours per day while animals are in the milking parlor area) to 100% where cattle are confined to housing during winter or harsh weather conditions. With few exceptions, swine production is completely confined which corresponds to 100% manure recovery.

Bedding material type (inert, organic), frequency of bedding, and quantity of material used add VS and fixed solids (FS) to the waste stream, which can increase CH₄ emissions. Organic materials range in size from larger particles (wood shavings) to rice hulls or recycled dried manure fiber. Swine are raised on concrete slats, allowing for urine and feces storage in pits below, and does not use bedding.

In warmer climates, water soakers, or misters, are used to reduce the heat load to cattle and pigs. This added water further dilutes the waste stream, if not evaporated from the animal or the waste stream, affecting emissions. Added water from flush manure collection (fresh water or reused liquid manure), and rainwater entering the waste stream can also affect the concentration of VS. Overall, reducing manure volume and VS content and increasing manure recovery assists in reducing manure GHG emissions using SLS.

FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS DURING THE SLS PROCESS

The separation process is often fast (minutes to hours) when compared to duration of manure management pre-separation (hours to days), or post-separation (weeks to months). Therefore, there is limited opportunity for GHG emissions during the SLS step itself. However, passive separation processes, such as gravity settling, require more time and a large open surface area; both factors increase opportunity for GHG emissions. Gravity SLS systems rely on gravity flow through a system over an extended retention time to remove solids. Gravity separation ponds or basins, or weeping wall systems, use a fill and dewater process to accumulate solids. The gravity separation ponds or basins have intermittent filling with dewatering resulting in crust formation. The crust develops over four to eight weeks or longer and is harvested with a slatted bucket to allow drainage or when dewatered with a tractor. Paired settling basins are operated to fill one and allow dewater while the other is filled. Solids are hauled out prior to switching back to the first basin. Anaerobic conditions in settling ponds or basins degrade VS as if they went directly to anaerobic storage, resulting in CH₄ emissions. The surface area of the gravity system likely becomes an N₂O emitting source during the wetting and drying processes. Climatic effects can influence emissions during this type of separation. In addition, higher wind speeds increase NH₃ emissions from wet manure surfaces.

The process of separation often involves using energy (electricity) and chemicals (polymers) to pump manure, actuate separator components, and coagulate solids. Management of solids requires additional energy (tractor or other heavy equipment). These resources are associated with their own indirect GHG emissions, referred to as scope 2 and scope 3 emissions, and out of the scope of this report.

Technical factors are the main drivers of GHG emissions from SLS, mainly, the separation efficiency, or how much VS and nitrogen follow the solid and liquid fractions. Separation efficiency will be key to determine downstream activities during storage and land application of both separated liquids and solids. Inefficient separator use can increase overall farm GHG emissions when combined effects of poor separation efficiency and indirect GHG emissions are considered. Separation efficiency can be calculated by the mass of the separated material divided by the mass of input material (see **Appendix A** for more details). Besides the type of separator, efficiency of separation is influenced by concentration of TS and VS in waste stream and proportion of various particle fractions of solids.

FACTORS AFFECTING GHG EMISSIONS AFTER SLS - DOWNSTREAM

Downstream activities from SLS encompass all manure handling operations following the separation process. These activities are the primary sources of GHG emissions and offer significant potential for GHG reductions compared to a traditional slurry/liquid manure system without manure processing.

Current models use VS content in stored manure as the main predictor of CH₄ emissions (**Appendix B**). As separated liquid manure contains fewer VS than unseparated slurry, CH₄ emissions during separated liquid storage are reduced. Moreover, CH₄ emissions from the separated solids are significantly lower compared to those from liquid storage. This reduction is due to the aerobic (with oxygen) conditions that inhibit CH₄ production and emission. As a result, the sum of CH₄ emissions from stored separated liquid manure and separated solid manure is lower than the CH₄ emissions from unseparated raw slurry storage. Other models, such as the Integrated Farm System Model (IFSM) differentiate the type of VS between degradable and non-degradable, with degradable VS responsible for nearly all emitted CH₄ (**Rotz et al., 2018**). However, there is currently no measured data on the separation of degradable VS between the separated liquid and solid manure.

Higher temperatures can increase CH₄ emissions from increased activity of CH₄ producing bacteria during storage. A strategy to minimize potential CH₄ emission is to avoid manure storage during warm months. However, this could also have unintended consequences for water quality that need to be considered. The size of the storage also affects emissions, particularly NH₃ as most inorganic nitrogen (in the form of ammonium), stays with the liquid fraction. The larger the surface area, the more opportunity for NH₃ to be volatilized due to increased exposure to the atmosphere and wind. These NH₃ emissions are reduced if an organic crust forms on top of the manure storage (more likely for dairy manure that has more fiber than swine manure), which acts as a barrier from wind. Given that separated liquids have reduced total solids vs unseparated manure, it is unlikely that a crust will form during storage of separated liquids. It is important to mention that sustained high temperatures (>50 °C) can stress methanogenic microorganisms and CH₄ production can decrease or stop.

There are other processing technologies that can be integrated into both separated liquid and solid manure management that can mitigate GHG emissions. Anaerobic digestion (AD) has been implemented

alongside SLS in various situations to improve dairy and swine manure management. AD is a biological process in which CH_4 is produced and recovered for use as fuel and energy source from manure using methanogens. This practice has been growing in popularity over the past decade. Acidification of separated liquids is another technology that can reduce pH, limiting growth of CH_4 and N_2O producing bacteria, and limiting conversion of nitrogen to NH_3 (Habtewold et al., 2018; Sokolov et al., 2020). Flocculation through chemicals has also been cited to further improve the separation efficiency of total solids that follow the solid manure stream, increasing the reduction of CH_4 emissions (Garcia et al., 2009).

While liquid manure storage after SLS clearly reduces CH_4 emissions, the net GHG benefits could be reduced when considering emissions from the separated manure solids. The magnitude of these emissions depends on the interaction of technical, environmental, and management practice factors outlined in **Table 1**.

A key management practice to minimize GHG emissions from separated solids is to keep them dry. When separated solids are too moist and stored for extended periods, anaerobic (without oxygen) pockets form, creating ideal conditions for N_2O and CH_4 emissions. Rapid utilization of these separated solids can also help minimize GHG emissions. Potential uses include on-farm animal bedding or off-farm transport for use as soil amendments. However, using separated solid manure as bedding recycles nitrogen, carbon, and volatile solids back into the system, which may further generate GHG emissions.

Composting is a popular method for utilizing separated solid manure, adding value to this solid stream. While composting effectively reduces CH_4 emissions, it can lead to increased N_2O emissions if not managed carefully (Garcia et al., 2009; Wang et al., 2017). Composting creates ideal conditions for N_2O emissions, including a mix of aerobic and anaerobic environments, high internal temperatures within compost piles, and elevated moisture levels that promote the activity of N_2O -forming microbes.

Research Evidence for GHG Emission Reductions After SLS

GHG emissions can be measured or modeled. At the same time, measured studies can be conducted at the farm or lab levels, with the gold standard being studies at the farm level as they are more representative of the management, environmental, and technical factors of current operating facilities. A literature review of 71 studies was conducted to identify reported separation efficiencies and GHG emission reductions. Of these studies, only 21 presented information on GHG emission reduction from SLS (**Table 2**). Overall, there is an agreement that SLS reduces CH_4 from the liquid fraction with an average 37% reduction when compared to unseparated manure. However, there is also agreement that NH_3 from the separated liquids and N_2O from the separated solids increase significantly (on a percentage basis) when compared to unseparated manure. For detailed information and more analysis on separation efficiencies and GHG emissions, visit (Appendix for Lit Review).

Table 2. Percent change in NH₃, N₂O, and CH₄ emissions from separated solid and liquid fractions compared with unseparated raw manure.

Animal manure	Technology	NH ₃		N ₂ O		CH ₄	
		Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid
Cattle							
Digestion	Roller Press (n=5)	-82.7	-26.3	74.1	-51.4	-68.7	-19.4
	Screw press (n=1)	-100.0	-30.1	-92.6	-31.7	-100.0	-100.0
Untreated	Screw press (n=6)	-94.0	14.8	460.4	-54.1	-84.2	-57.5
	Screw press + PAM (n=1)	-97.2	58.6	740.6	-64.4	-79.3	-84.0
Swine							
Untreated	Screw press (n=3)	-96.3	-9.1	10,187.9	183.6	-92.5	-21.4
	PAM+rotating screen+filter press+air flotation (n= 2)	-13.0	-12.1	na	na	na	na
Acidification	Screw press (n=1)	-74.5	235.1	1,139.5	37.5	-15.7	-41.9
Digestion	Screw press (n=1)	-27.0	824.5	-48.0	-97.3	-96.9	37.5
Acidification +digestion	Screw press (n=1)	-93.9	-49.7	-66.8	-64.1	-58.3	-6.2

N₂O increases of >100% might be explained by almost negligible baseline measurement from the unseparated manure and an increase in N₂O emissions from separated stored manure. This highlights that for trace gases, reporting the absolute value of the gases (and the reductions) is more important than the percentages. Moreover, the significant percentage increase in N₂O emissions could be exacerbated when expressing changes in kg CO₂-eq given the high characterization factor of N₂O (273).

In terms of net GHG impacts, studies evaluating the entire manure management lifecycle after SLS agree that, despite an increase in N₂O emissions from separated solids, this increase is not as significant to cancel the reduction in CH₄ emissions from stored separated liquid manure. As a result, there is evidence to conclude that SLS can effectively mitigate GHG emissions, with reductions from manure storage ranging from 30% to 58% with centrifuges achieving higher reductions from higher separation of VS (Aguirre-Villegas et al., 2019; Amon et al., 2006; Fangueiro et al., 2008; Holly et al., 2017; Lyons et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2017; Wright and Gooch, 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). The wide range of GHG emission reductions depends on the interaction between the separation technology, the factors presented in Table 1, and the defined baselines of the comparisons.

Figure 1. Drivers of emissions upstream, during, and downstream solid-liquid separation. The confidence of magnitude and direction of all these emissions dependent on interactions of factors presented in **Table 1**.

Practice Implementation

A rigorous operation and maintenance plan is essential for continued and consistent operation of SLS systems. This includes all components of SLS equipment (pumps, screens, flocculant dosing apparatus,

etc.) and management of separated solids to prevent anaerobic conditions conducive to CH₄ and N₂O emissions. Good technological resources can perform poorly when management is not up to par. Less impressive technological resources may perform reasonably well under stringent management. Implementing SLS does not automatically result in reduced GHG emissions. Equipment must operate effectively. These conditions might be even more important for gravity separation systems. Frequent and complete cleanout of gravity separation systems and immediate drying or managed compost are necessary to minimize formation of undesired conditions yielding gaseous emissions.

Gravity, mechanical and chemical separation technologies yield potentially different waste streams. Regular analysis of resultant waste streams is essential to incorporate solids and liquids into nutrient management plans. Often separated solids are high in organic nitrogen making them less desirable for plant nitrogen needs as organic nitrogen must mineralize and/or nitrify to be available to plants for uptake. These organic solids have the potential to improve soil tilth and porosity and improve water holding capacity. Depending on the SLS process, the resultant liquid's organic N and/or phosphorus removal may have occurred successfully. Absent chemical intervention, soluble ions remain in the liquid fraction. Ratios of liquid and solid end products may make them more or less desirable for use in agronomic application to land depending on site specific nutrient management needs and restrictions.

SLS technologies vary in complexity and modes of operation. Reports indicate that repeat interruption to operation due to blockages, screen occlusion (blinding), mechanical failure of equipment, imprecise polymer dosing/addition are not uncommon. These issues lead to reduced separation performance or complete stoppage. A sound and consistent operation and maintenance plan is necessary to ensure effective running of SLS systems. In addition, these operational issues reduce the effectiveness of the SLS technology as a GHG mitigation intervention and can result in increased emissions when energy (electricity or fuel) is employed to manage the residual waste streams.

For an example of measuring, monitoring, reporting, and verifying (MMRV) strategies for GHGs after SLS refer to **Appendix C**.

Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of solid-liquid separation and its impact on greenhouse gas emissions. It begins by outlining the primary drivers of emissions from manure management and the methods used for reporting these emissions. The core of the technical note delves into the principles behind emission reductions at various stages—upstream, downstream, and during the solid-liquid separation process itself. It explains the individual factors contributing to emissions, while considering the interplay between environmental, technical, and management aspects. Additionally, the document summarizes existing literature on emission reductions achieved through solid-liquid separation and identifies key factors for effective implementation. Finally, **Appendix D** highlights areas requiring further research.

Additional Resources

- Chapter 4 – Solid-liquid separation alternatives for manure handling treatment, 2019, USDA-NRCS. Part 637 Environmental Engineering National Engineering Handbook. Available at: <https://directives.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files2/1712930729/29499.pdf>
- Dairy conservation navigator <https://www.dairyconservation.org/>

Appendix

A. ESTIMATION OF SEPARATION EFFICIENCY

Separation efficiency can be calculated by the mass of the separated material divided by the mass of input material (Svarovsky, 2001). This is the difference of the mass of TS and VS in influent into and out of the system ($Mass_i - Mass_e$) when expressed as a percent of the total mass of TS and VS in the influent ($Mass_i$); $Mass_i - Mass_e / Mass_i * 100$ (Moller et al., 2007). If quantifiable, one can subtract out the TS and VS in flush water (when concentrations and quantity are known). Additionally, TS and VS separated can be quantified. This procedure works better under laboratory conditions when volumes can be measured and sampled. Under field conditions, less precise methods may be used that rely on multiple grab samples of separator influent (SI) and separator effluent (SE). Quantification of the concentrations of TS and VS in flush water used to collect the waste stream and the added volume of water used to flush manure is more important as SI is more diluted or concentration of TS and VS in flush water influent is higher.

B. EQUATION TO ESTIMATE CH₄ EMISSIONS FROM SLURRY/LIQUID MANURE STORAGE

$$CH_4 = VS * 365 * B_0 * MCF * 0.67 \quad \text{Eq A}$$

Simplified CH₄ equation from the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2019) considering only slurry/liquid manure storage, where CH₄: methane emissions (kg CH₄/year); VS: volatile solids (kg/day); 365: days in the year; B₀: maximum methane-producing capacity (m³ CH₄/kg VS), MCF: methane conversion factor, as decimal (dimensionless), 0.67: Conversion factor from m³ of methane to kg of methane.

C. MEASURING, MONITORING, REPORTING, AND VERIFYING (MMRV) STRATEGIES FOR GHGS AFTER SLS

Supply chain businesses rely on third party vendors to measure, monitor, report, and verify (MMRV) GHG reductions. A common verification process uses estimates based on animal housing and milk production records to estimate manure collected and the fraction entering storage. Third party verifiers collect data monthly (milk production, animals present, service reports for equipment maintenance, cleaning screens and bills for parts replacement, utility records to demonstrate running). There is also annual verification of management practices in place at each facility. Solids accumulation in storage is estimated or calculated. Calculated emissions from separated solids can use emissions estimates of storage or compost. However, few research papers quantify emissions of N₂O or CH₄ under farm conditions. They do identify increased nitrate in compost and increased NH₃ emissions. Improper management of separated solids may create a net increase in GHG emissions through CH₄ and N₂O.

D. NEEDS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Solid-liquid separation is a promising technology to reduce GHG emissions, but there are still many variables that need further research or different reporting to quantify and determine these reductions more precisely. The following needs have been identified:

- When reporting emissions, it is essential to present both cumulative and absolute values. Simply showing reduction changes as percentages is not sufficient, particularly for trace gases measured from unseparated manure. An increase in these gases after separation can lead to a significant percentage change. This is especially crucial for nitrous oxide (N₂O), which has a much higher characterization factor (273) compared to carbon dioxide (CO₂).
- There is a need to relate and measure C:N ratio from unseparated and separated manure on a continuous basis to relate CH₄ and NH₃ emissions, while also evaluating the interaction with other factors such as pH and temperature.
- Differentiate the different fiber fractions in both raw manure and separated manure. This can include measuring the lignin, hemicellulose, and cellulose content in raw and separated manure to predict methane emissions more effectively, the same way current literature

evaluates enteric CH₄. Within volatile solids, these include the degradable vs the non-degradable volatile solids.

- Lack of differentiation between methane potential (B₀) from unseparated manure vs separated manure. Modeling studies predicting methane emissions from separated liquid manure use the same B₀ but, there are changes on degradable volatile solids that need to be further explored.
- Analyze the effect of bedding in systems with solid-liquid separation. If separated solids are used as bedding, how do those re-introduced solids affect the overall GHG emissions of the system?
- Future studies should report the management practices to identify the main drivers of GHGs within the evaluated farm systems. It has been observed that some current studies do not even report manure characteristics in the current literature (e.g., TS, VS, OrgN, TAN). Knowing management practices is key to further understanding the main drivers of GHG emissions from down and upstream solid-liquid separation.
- There is a need for studies to report mass balances of separated fractions (both solids and liquids) and manure constituents from experimental designs, so that GHGs can be modeled.
- Despite that there are experimental studies analyzing both manure constituents and GHG emissions after solid-liquid separation, there is a need for more measurement studies at the farm level. Laboratory studies present the ideal conditions and that might not be representative of management at the farm level.
- Related to the previous point, it is crucial for experimental studies at the farm level to report not only the management practices, but the condition of the solid-liquid separation technology. Is it functioning as designed? Does it need maintenance?
- More research analyzing the effect of solid-liquid separation on GHG and ammonia emissions from land application of the separated liquid and solid-fractions. The pool of available studies analyze the effect of GHG on storage after separation, but literature is limited or non-existent for the lifecycle of manure management after solid liquid separation vs baselines. There is a need for more comprehensive studies tracking emissions and manure characteristics across the manure lifecycle. Isolating individual emissions and/or steps does not show the potential trade-offs as there are many interactions that can affect the net impact on system emissions.

References

- Aguirre-Villegas, H.A., Larson, R.A., Sharara, M.A., 2019. Anaerobic digestion, solid-liquid separation, and drying of dairy manure: Measuring constituents and modeling emission. *Science of the Total Environment* 696, 134059. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134059>
- Amon, B., Kryvoruchko, V., Amon, T., Zechmeister-Boltenstern, S., 2006. Methane, nitrous oxide and ammonia emissions during storage and after application of dairy cattle slurry and influence of slurry treatment. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 112, 153–162. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2005.08.030>

- Fangueiro, D., Senbayran, M., Trindade, H., Chadwick, D., 2008. Cattle slurry treatment by screw press separation and chemically enhanced settling: Effect on greenhouse gas emissions after land spreading and grass yield. *Bioresour Technol* 99, 7132–7142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2007.12.069>
- Garcia, M.C., Szogi, A.A., Vanotti, M.B., Chastain, J.P., Millner, P.D., 2009. Enhanced solid–liquid separation of dairy manure with natural flocculants. *Bioresour Technol* 100, 5417–5423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.BIORTECH.2008.11.012>
- Habtewold, J., Gordon, R., Sokolov, V., VanderZaag, A., Wagner-Riddle, C., Dunfield, K., 2018. Reduction in methane emissions from acidified dairy slurry is related to inhibition of methanosarcina species. *Front Microbiol* 9, 420272. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FMICB.2018.02806/BIBTEX>
- Holly, M.A., Larson, R.A., Powell, J.M., Ruark, M.D., Aguirre-Villegas, H., 2017. Greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions from digested and separated dairy manure during storage and after land application. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.02.007>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2019. Chapter 10: Emissions from Livestock and Manure Management, in: Calvo Buendia, E., Tanabe, K., Kranjc, A., Baasansuren, J., Fukuda, M., Ngarize, S., Osako, A., Pyrozhenko, Y., Shermanau, P., Federici, S. (Eds.), *Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories*. IPCC, Switzerland.
- Lyons, G.A., Cathcart, A., Frost, J.P., Wills, M., Johnston, C., Ramsey, R., Smyth, B., 2021. Review of Two Mechanical Separation Technologies for the Sustainable Management of Agricultural Phosphorus in Nutrient-Vulnerable Zones. *Agronomy* 2021, Vol. 11, Page 836 11, 836. <https://doi.org/10.3390/AGRONOMY11050836>
- Moller, H.B., Hansen, J.D., Sorensen, C.A.G., 2007. Nutrient Recovery by Solid-Liquid Separation and Methane Productivity of Solids. *Trans ASABE* 50, 193–200. <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.22400>
- Rotz, C., Corson, M., Chianese, D., Hafner, S., Jarvis, R., Coiner, C., 2018. *The Integrated Farm System Model - Reference Manual - Version 4.4*, pp. 250. Pennsylvania.
- Sokolov, V., VanderZaag, A., Habtewold, J., Dunfield, K., Tambong, J.T., Wagner-Riddle, C., Venkiteswaran, J.J., Gordon, R., 2020. Acidification of Residual Manure in Liquid Dairy Manure Storages and Its Effect on Greenhouse Gas Emissions. *Front Sustain Food Syst* 4, 568648. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FSUFS.2020.568648/BIBTEX>
- Svarovsky, L., 2001. Efficiency of separation of particles from fluids. *Solid-Liquid Separation* 66–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-075064568-3/50027-4>
- Wang, Y., Dong, H., Zhu, Z., Gerber, P.J., Xin, H., Smith, P., Opio, C., Steinfeld, H., Chadwick, D., 2017. Mitigating Greenhouse Gas and Ammonia Emissions from Swine Manure Management: A System Analysis. *Environ Sci Technol* 51, 4503–4511. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.6b06430>
- Wright, P., Gooch, C., 2022. GREENHOUSE GAS FROM DAIRY MANURE MANAGEMENT AT THE FARMSTEAD. Part 8: GHG reduction from solid-liquid separation systems [WWW Document]. URL <https://ecommons.cornell.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/db51f129-156d-483c-a5c3-7b3a9b0290d4/content> (accessed 6.1.25).

Zhang, X., Liu, C., Liao, W., Wang, S., Zhang, W., Xie, J., Gao, Z., 2022. Separation efficiency of different solid-liquid separation technologies for slurry and gas emissions of liquid and solid fractions: A meta-analysis. *J Environ Manage* 310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114777>